

Thermogravimetric Analysis of Some Aluminium Soaps

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Thermal behaviour of tri-soaps, isopropoxide soaps, and chloride soaps of aluminium has been studied and the loss in weight due to decomposition at different temperatures recorded by an automatic recording thermogravimetric balance. The stepwise decompositions have been postulated by isolating the respective ketones and taking into account the total loss at different temperatures.

For the thermogravimetric analysis various types of soaps (tri-soaps, alkoxide soaps, and chloride soaps) of aluminium were heated inside the furnace of an automatic recording thermobalance (Stanton). The balance has a controlled rate of heating (250°/hr.) and the weight of the sample is recorded at each temperature automatically. The weights of the samples were plotted on a calibrated graph against the temperature of heating. The plots are shown in Figs. 1-3; these may be called 'decomposition curves'. The data have been used for plotting the differential thermal graphs (D. T. G.) by recording the loss in weight per five minutes against the temperature of heating.

The decomposition curves (Fig. 1) obtained on heating the tri-soaps (laurate and palmitate) show that they remain stable up to ~ 200°, above which the decomposition appears to take place according to the reaction:

The evolution of carbon dioxide appears to be completed at about 300°, after which the ketone formed begins to decompose. The differential thermal graph (Fig. 4) depicts that the various ketones show a characteristic peak in their decomposition rates. The position of this peak appears to depend only on the nature of the fatty acid group and for the same group, it occurs at almost the same temperature, irrespective of the nature of the aluminium soap, i.e., in tri-soaps, chloride soaps as well as alkoxide soaps (Table I). Even in soaps of lanthanum and other rare earths, peaks occur in the same temperature range. The formation of ketones in the thermal decomposition of the soaps has been confirmed by their actual isolation and identification in a number of cases. The 'Decomposition' and 'D.T.G.' curves are given only for one characteristic soap in each case. Similar results were obtained in a number of other products (Table I).

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1. Misra *et al.*, private communication.

TABLE I

Maximum decomposition temperature of various soaps.

Soap.	Formula.	Ketone.	Formula.	*Temp.
Al trilaurate	Al(OOC.C ₁₁ H ₂₃) ₃	Laurone	C ₂₃ H ₄₆ O	380°
Al mono-isopropoxide di-laurate	Al(OPr ⁱ)(OOC.C ₁₁ H ₂₃) ₂	Laurone	C ₂₃ H ₄₆ O	380°
Al tripalmitate	Al(OOC.C ₁₅ H ₃₁) ₃	Palmitone	C ₃₁ H ₆₂ O	420°
Al monohydroxy mono-isopropoxide mono-palmitate	Al(OH)(OPr ⁱ)(OOC.C ₁₅ H ₃₁)	Palmitone	C ₃₁ H ₆₂ O	420°
Al oxide stearate	O = Al(OOC.C ₁₇ H ₃₅) ₂	Stearone	C ₃₅ H ₇₀ O	440°
Al monochloride di-stearate	AlCl(OOC.C ₁₇ H ₃₅) ₂	Stearone	C ₃₅ H ₇₀ O	440°
Al dichloride mono-stearate	AlCl ₂ (OOC.C ₁₇ H ₃₅)	Stearone	C ₃₅ H ₇₀ O	440°
Al mono-isopropoxide di-behenate	Al(OPr ⁱ)(OOC.C ₂₁ H ₄₃) ₂	Behenone	C ₄₃ H ₈₆ O	445°
Al di-isopropoxide mono-behenate	Al(OPr ⁱ) ₂ (OOC.C ₂₁ H ₄₃)	Behenone	C ₄₃ H ₈₆ O	445°

*At which the decomposition of ketone is maximum.

Compared to the above tri-soaps, the isopropoxide soaps (mono-isopropoxide di-laurate, mono-isopropoxide di-behenate, and di-isopropoxide mono-behenate) begin to decompose at a lower temperature of about 120°. The corresponding decomposition curves (Fig. 2) and D. T. G. (Fig. 5) show a slow loss in weight below 230-270°. The loss in weight (below 230° in the case of mono-isopropoxide di-laurate and 260-275° in the case of behenate soap) corresponds almost to reactions (I) and (II):

Above this temperature, there appears to be further decomposition with evolution of carbon dioxide according to reactions (III) and (IV):

The evolution of carbon dioxide also appears to be completed at about 300° in every case (Fig. 4). Above 300°, the main decomposition appears to be that of the ketone formed.

When monohydroxy mono-isopropoxide mono-palmitate, obtained by hydrolysing the di-isopropoxide mono-palmitate with an equimolar quantity of water, was heated similarly, the decomposition started below 100°. The thermal graph (Fig. 2) shows gradual decomposition of the soap. The decomposition curve (Fig. 2) appears to be in agreement with the following plausible mechanism:

The second stage was also proved by heating aluminium oxide stearate alone (Fig. 3).

A similar study has been carried out in the case of chloride soaps of aluminium (Fig. 3). The chloride soaps decompose with the formation of hydrogen chloride by absorbing moisture from the atmosphere above 120°. By making a comparative decomposition study (Fig. 3) of the monochloride di-stearate and dichloride mono-stearate and by taking into account the loss in weight of the samples above 120°, the following probable decomposition mechanism may be suggested:

The above stearate soaps show a maximum rate of decomposition at about 440°.

Temp.
FIG. 2

AA : Al monohydroxy mono-isopropoxide mono-palmitate.
 BB : Al di-isopropoxide mono-behenate.
 CC : Al mono-isopropoxide di-laurate.
 DD : Al mono-isopropoxide di-behenate.

AA : Aluminium oxide
 stearate.
 BB : Al dichloride
 mono-stearate.
 CC : Al monochloride
 di-stearate.

EXPERIMENTAL

Aluminium tri-soaps (trilaurate and tripalmitate) and chloride soaps (monochloride distearate and dichloride monostearate) were prepared by the interaction of aluminium chloride and fatty acids in hydrocarbon solvents². Isopropoxide soaps (mono-isopropoxide dilaurate, mono-isopropoxide dibehenate, di-isopropoxide monobehenate) were prepared by the method of Pande and Mehrotra³.

These soaps were dried under reduced pressure and heated inside the furnace of an automatic recording thermogravimetric balance (Stanton.) A weighed quantity of the compound was taken in a silica crucible and was heated with a constant rise of temperature ($250^{\circ}/\text{hr.}$). The furnace was switched on and the loss in weight of the compound with the continuous rise in temperature was recorded on a calibrated graphical chart supplied by the manufacturers. The loss due to buoyancy was obtained by heating an empty crucible from room temperature to 800° . The error due to buoyancy was found almost negligible to about 300° and then it increased slowly. In most of the experiments, the aluminium soaps yielded the oxide in the temperature range of 600° where the buoyancy error was found to be about 8-10 mg. The above effects due to buoyancy were taken into consideration for the losses in weights at different temperatures.

FIG. 4
D.T.G record for Al trilaurate.

Tri-laurate (0.312 g., 0.0005*M*), tri-palmitate (0.791 g., 0.001*M*), mono-isopropoxide di-laurate (0.484 g., 0.001*M*), mono-isopropoxide di-behenate (0.383 g., 0.0005*M*), di-isopropoxide mono-behenate (0.484 g., 0.001*M*), monohydroxy mono-isopropoxide mono-palmitate (0.688 g., 0.00192*M*), oxide stearate (0.650 g., 0.002*M*), monochloride di-stearate (0.628 g., 0.001*M*), and dichloride mono-stearate (0.762 g., 0.002*M*) of aluminium on heating were found to decompose slowly. The losses in weight with the rise of temperature are shown in Figs. 1-3.

These losses in weight at various temperatures correspond within $\pm 2\%$ to the proposed mechanism in each case. The tri-laurate, tri-palmitate, and oxide-stearate soaps appear to be stable to about 200° and the evolution of carbon dioxide is complete at 300° , 305° , and 330° respectively. In the case of isopropoxide and chloride soaps, the decomposition starts at about 120° and the evolution of isopropanol and hydrogen chloride appears to be complete at about $230-50^{\circ}$ in the case of di-soaps and $280-320^{\circ}$ in the case of mono-soaps. The monohydroxy mono-isopropoxy palmitate is the least stable and begins to decompose at a much lower temperature (about 80°). The decomposition of all the above soaps appears to be completed at about 600° .

2. Rai and Mehrotra, this *Journal*, 1962, 39, 1.

3. Mehrotra and Pande, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1956, 2, 1; 1957, 4, 128.

The thermogravimetric curve in each case shows a maximum (Table I), which is due to the ketone liberated, as has been confirmed by running the thermogravimetric curves for the ketones themselves. In order to substantiate further the formation of the corresponding ketones, the various soaps were heated in a crucible at 400° in a Muffle furnace for 20 to 30 minutes after which these were lixiviated with ethanol. The soluble portions were repeatedly crystallised from ethanol and then identified by their melting points (laurone, 70°; palmitone, 83°; stearone, 88°; behenone, 96°) and positive tests for the ketonic groups.

Temp.
FIG. 5

D.T.G. record for Al di-isopropoxide
mono-behenate.

Temp.
FIG. 6

D.T.G. record for Al monochloride
di-stearate.

It may be of interest to record that in a recent study, Kambe *et al.*⁴ have similarly proved the formation of ketones in cobalt stearates.

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